

Internal Dimensions of Maya Angelou being a Child, an Artist, a Mother and a Social Activist

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Abstract

Maya Angelou believes that the real history is created by ordinary people. For her, the endless source of inspiration for writing used to lie in “amazingly noble human beings” and their sufferings. Maya Angelou is an African writer and social activist, who has been fighting against racial discrimination and women’s issues, ever since she started holding a pen for a purpose. The paper attempts to explore the internal Dimensions of Maya Angelou being a Child, an Artist, a Mother and a Social Activist.

Keywords: liberation, sufferings, oppression, social prejudice.

Maya Angelou is one of the most renowned and influential voices of present world. She is celebrated poet, memoirist, novelist, educator, dramatist, producer, actress, historian, filmmaker and civil rights activist. She has published seven autobiographies, many books of essays, numerous books of poetry and is credited with long list of plays, movies and television shows. Maya Angelou is one of the most decorated writers of generation, with dozens of awards and over thirty honorary doctoral degrees. With the publication of her first autobiography *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings* (1969), deals of her first seventeen years, and brought her international recognition and acclaim. She was heralded as a new kind of memoirist.

As a person who dramatizes the songs and dances of various old traditions. She is in the position of giving dramatic expressions to other people’s words and music. But it is only in *The Heart of Woman*, the fourth of Maya Angelou’s autobiographical series, does she begin the difficult task of giving voice to her own narrative. In the more personal opening sequence of a *The Heart of A Woman* published in 1981. Maya Angelou and her son Guy are living communality on a houseboat near San Francisco, trying to bridge the gap between black and white and living on the savings which Maya Angelou had earned in California and Hawaii. After a year Maya Angelou and Guy move from the commune to a rented house near San Francisco and finally in 1959, they cross the continent to New York City. *The Heart of A Woman* begins in the following atmosphere.

As a story opens, Maya Angelou and Guy have moved from the security of Vivian Baxter’s home to a houseboat near San Francisco

that they share with four Whites. Her connection to her white roommates parallels her affinities with Kerouac, Ginsberg and other liberated white writers of the 1950s. Maya Angelou is still somewhat distrustful of White people. She does not describe either her character or the characters of her roommates in a positive way. She never names the people with whom she lives for almost a year, even though “naming” has been an important process in Maya Angelou’s writing. As autobiographer, Maya Angelou hastily bypasses the year on the houseboat, giving the impression that it was either, too unpleasant, too embracing or too trivial to recollect. However it is an evidence to prove the researcher that things have changed and the relationship between blacks and whites became liberal especially in areas in San Francisco.

In The Heart of A Woman Maya Angelou is seen as some what a relaxed woman becoming imaginative with her hairstyle and clothing. She particularly enjoys the experiment because her roommates neither ignore Maya Angelou’s and Guy’s skin colour nor do they romanticize it. Maya Angelou’s sojourn in a commune reveals her capacity for co-operation and anticipates her later group involvements with writers, actors and civil rights workers. Within a year, Maya Angelou is tired of sharing space and longs for privacy. She makes an unsuccessful attempt to rent a small house in a segregated white neighbourhood. But once again the theme of racial discrimination crops up as renting a house is not at all possible for the black people as the landlords mostly prefer the whites. Maya Angelou begins to encounter the racial prejudices similar to the episodes in *I Know Why the Caged Birds Sings*, where dentist Lincoln refused to look into her mouth or in *Gather Together in My Name*, when the saleswoman in Stamps insults her. “We do not interrupt students during class, for anyone. And we do not make a student a special case, just because he happens to be Negro. And we do not allow Negro boys to use foul language in front of our girls” (19).

Maya Angelou moves further to present the pain of social prejudice by deciding to change the school and the area “where black skin was not regarded as one of nature’s more unsightly mistakes” (21). She decides to move to the Westlake district where Mexican, black American, Asian and white families lives side by side in old rambling houses. Maya Angelou also finds the neighbours cordial and they speak with each other as they mowed their lawns or shaped in the long-established local grocery stores. Maya Angelou describes her new area thus:

I rented the second floor of a two-story Victorian, and when Guy saw the black children playing on our new street, he was giddy with excitement. His reaction made me see how much he had missed the close contact with black people. “Boy!” He jumped and wriggled “Boy! Now, I’m going to make some friends! (21)

Maya Angelou becomes more relaxed in Westlake district. She begins to write sketches, songs and stories. She also meets the celebrated African American novelist John Killens who is in California writing a screen play from one of his novels *Youngblood*. Killens reads through her material, urging her to come to New York, where she will get feedback from other aspiring black writers. The first dramatic change in Maya Angelou’s character in *The Heart of a Women* occurs when mother and son move to New York, where she and Guy live with John and Grace Killens and their family in Brooklyn until they find an apartment of their own. Guy is at first skeptical and disapproving but they soon settle in by attending schools, meeting neighbours and “grappling” with differences they discover in leaving the West for the East. Maya Angelou now seems confident in her lifestyle, her self-assurance deriving in part from the close relationships she is able to form with black singers, actors and writers. Maya Angelou got an opportunity to move with Martin Luther King Jr. as she was introduced to a fund-raising project at the Village Gate by one Mr. Cambridge at a popular night club in Greenwich Village to benefit the Southern Christian Leadership Conference (SCLC). Called “Cabaret for Freedom” the fund-raiser is created, directed and performed by Maya

Angelou and Cambridge with help from comics, dancers and other theatre people. Yet despite the cabaret project and a developing personal friendship, Maya Angelou and Cambridge never become lovers.

In *The Heart of a Woman* Maya Angelou becomes a far more public person than she was in the earlier volumes. She begins to identify with emerging civil-rights movement after working on the fund-raiser programme. Eventually Maya Angelou becomes Northern Coordinator of the Southern Christian Leadership Conference (SCLC). She is also committed to a women's organization called the Cultural Association for Women of African Heritage (CAWAH). Soon after meeting the South African hero Vusumzi Make in 1961, Maya Angelou and the women of CAWAH almost halt the operations of the UN General Assembly when they conduct a sit-in at the United Nations building after the Prime Minister Zaire and Patrice Lumumba are assassinated in 1961. Maya Angelou and her friend Rosa Guy sought the support of Black Muslim leader Malcom X. Maya Angelou and Rosa hoped that he and his organization with support the activities of CAWAH and make use of the energy incited by the protest gathering. But on the contrary Malcolm X did not approve the protest strategy. Even though Maya Angelou is disappointed with Malcolm X's response, but she is entranced by his good looks and his fire, traits that had also attracted her to South African rebel Vusumzi Make. The second major change in Maya Angelou's character occurs in *The Heart of a Woman*, when she meets Vusumzi Make, a freedom fighter recently released from a South African prison.

Vus Make appears to be the perfect choice for her husband as a handsome dazzling intellectual, given Maya Angelou's desire to be loved and her growing concern for Africa liberation movements. Meanwhile, Maya Angelou is already engaged to a bail bondsman, Thomas Allan, a smooth man of "reddish-tan colour" who gives her "lavish satisfaction" (100). But Vus Make is electrifying, exciting and beautiful. If she marries Thomas, Maya Angelou would always regret her decision. Vus and Maya Angelou go through the emotions of marrying in England but such a thing never happened in Maya Angelou's life. Maya Angelou reflects thus:

At the end of the string of parties, Vus and I left for England, leaving Guy in the home of Pete and T.Beveridge, who lived a few blocks from my Brooklyn house. We sat on the plane holding hands, kissing, seeing our future as a realm of struggle and eternal victory. Vus said we would marry in Oxford, such a pretty little town. I explained that I wanted have my mother and son present at my wedding and asked if we could wait. (133)

But in London Maya Angelou and Vus begin to spend less time together. Maya Angelou starts associating with a community of middle-class African women who warn her that marriage to a African freedom fighter can often lead to desertion. As Maya Angelou listens to her sisters' stories about their struggles and colonialism, she enthalls them with heroic tales about African American women. As Vus Make continues to neglect Maya Angelou, she again proves herself vulnerable to male authority as she was with Curly, L.D., Tollbrook, Tosh Angelos and other men in her past. In her role as Vus Make's wife, Maya Angelou is confronted for the second time with the struggle between being a home-maker and being a professional, as she had struggled in her earlier autobiographies between being a mother and being a professional. As an African who had been trained only to see women as subservient, Vus Make is culturally insensitive to Maya Angelou's needs as a working woman.

In one such hilarious sequence that occurs before they are a couple, Maya Angelou accompanies Vus to a Cocktail party in the Manhattan suite of a West African ambassador. Even though she was wearing her most flattering dress and can speak fluently about international politics in several languages, the guests ignore her because she is an American woman. Maya Angelou's way out

of this embarrassment is to sit in the kitchen drinking gin with the black female cook. When Vus discovers Maya Angelou, he is humiliated and furious. Maya Angelou reflects thus:

Vus began to talk. I was his wife, the wife of an African leader. I had embarrassed him. Sitting in the kitchen, getting drunk with the cook. When he tried to talk to me, I had laughed in his face. No African lady would bring such disgrace on her husband. I looked at the other people in the elevator, but they averted their white faces. As neither Vus nor I existed in their real world, they simply had to wait until we reached the ground floor and then our sounds and shadows would disappear. (203)

Vus chases the drunken Maya Angelou around the lobby of the classy building where she eludes him, grabs a cab out from under the nose of a waiting woman and spends the night with her novelist – friend Rosa Guy. If Vus could be so uncompromising in New York, one can imagine his attitude when they move to Cairo. He expects Maya Angelou to honour the Egyptian custom of the husband providing for the wife. Moreover, Maya Angelou accepts a position as associate editor with the *Arab Observer* without getting Vus's permission. In a torrent of fury, he reproaches her, suggesting that she is a man. All is chaos until a mutual friend and American journalist, David DuBois, persuades Vus that her salary would help them serve the revolutionary cause. David DuBois encourages Maya Angelou thus:

“Darling, you are a wonderful woman. Excuse the harsh words. You're not arrogant. You are thoughtful. I appreciate your idea. But it's not possible. You'll never find work in Cairo.” “Vus, I have a job. Associate editor of the *Arab Observer*. I start tomorrow.” I watched the disbelief on his face turn to anger, then to rage. “You took a job without consulting me? Are you a man?” He stood and began to pace over the expensive rug. His tirade carried him from the sofa to the entry, over to the large chair and back to stand in front of me. His vilification included my insolence, independence, lack of respect, arrogance, ignorance, defiance, callousness, cheekiness and lack of breeding. I sat, watching him, listening and thinking. He was right. Somewhere in his swarm of words he had my apt description. I also understood that may be I had gone too far. Even an American black man would have found such a headstrong wife unsuitable, and how much more an African husband, steeped in a tradition of at least the appearance of male authority. (226-227)

During the course of time Maya Angelou begins to realize that Vus Make is too friendly with other women and too irresponsible with money. Their irreconcilable position toward fidelity and financial commitment require that they be examined. They decide to get separated and move the Egyptian court of law. The tribunal decides in Maya Angelou's favour but asks her to stay with Vus for six more months. Maya Angelou agrees but when there is a job offer from Liberia, in West Africa, Maya Angelou accepts it.

Maya Angelou's disastrous relationship with Vus Make evokes certain comparisons and contrasts to her marriage with Tosh Angelos in *Singin'* and *Swingin'* and *Gettin' Merry Like Christmas*. It also recalls the failed marriage between Bailey Johnson Sr. and Vivian Baxters with its negative impact on Maya Angelou's life as a child and a woman. In the course of her life, Maya Angelou introduces problems or conditions that echo other volumes giving them unity or offering points of contrast.

The most valuable aspect of her relationship with Vus Make is its connection to her growing romance with Africa. In the fourth and fifth volumes, Africa is a site of her growth – first in Cairo, the capital of Egypt and then in Accra, the Capital of Ghana. In these tightly interrelated volumes, Maya Angelou initiates a search for her ancestral past. A developing writer, her continuing identification with language and character makes her sensitive to her African roots. Maya Angelou begins to articulate her connections to African slaves who had been “shackled with chains” and made to carry the weight of their fears with the weight of their irons (257). Maya Angelou reflects thus:

I could look down from my window seat and see trees, and bushes, reveres and dense forest. It all began here. The jumble of poverty-stricken children sleeping in rat-infested tenements or abandoned cars. The terrifying moan of my grandmother, "Bread of Heaven, Bread of Heaven, feed me till I want no more." The drugged days and alcoholic nights of men for whom hope had not been born. The loneliness of women who would never know appreciation or a mite's share of honor. Here, there, along the banks of that river, someone was taken, tied with ropes, shackled with chains, forced to march for weeks carrying the double burden of neck irons and abysmal fear. In that large clump of trees, looking like wood moss from the plane's great height, boys and girls had been hunted like beasts, caught and tethered together. Sacrificial lambs on the altar of greed. America's period of orgiastic lynchings had begun on yonder broad savannah. (257)

Near the end of *The Heart of A Woman*, Maya Angelou meets her greatest challenge when Guy's car is hit by a truck outside of Accra. An old couple found him on the road and brought him to the emergency ward. At the hospital while her son lies on a stretcher, Maya Angelou contemplates his rich golden skin "turned to ash-grey" (263). The deliberate repetition of her terror creates both an emotional link between the two volumes and underscores the impact of Guy's injuries on both character and story line. The repetitions of car accidents in each volume of the autobiography heightens the dramatic effect and gives them intensity not achieved anywhere else in the series.

As in *Singin'* and *Swingin'* and *Gettin' Merry Like Christmas*, *The Heart of A Woman* Maya Angelou remains in a state of flux, continuously open to changes in her life. These changes even involve her divorce from Vus Make and her suffering over her injured son. As she faces these problems, she continues the process of redefining her self. In *The Heart of A Woman*, Maya Angelou's more stable character derives from the self-assurance that comes from long years of living and mothering, her success with writing and her engagements in theatre and politics.

Maya Angelou's self-assurance hinted at in earlier volumes is heightened in a *The Heart of A Woman* which is a major aspect of her character. As it is already observed, motherhood is the dominant theme in each of the autobiography of Maya Angelou. But it takes on a new complexity in *The Heart of A Woman* owing to the presence and absence of Maya Angelou's mother, Vivian Baxter. The complications of the motherhood theme can be demonstrated by dividing it into three different issues namely Maya Angelou mothering Guy, Vivian mothering Maya Angelou and Maya Angelou mothering herself. In the opening sequences of the book, Maya Angelou defends Guy on two different occasions when he is accused of misconduct at school. She also tries to protect him against the outrageous tirades of blues singer Billie Holiday. As she gets ready to leave for New York, Maya Angelou observes that her son is changing that he is at the age of fourteen, "growing into a tall aloof stranger" (22). Despite his aloofness, Guy and his mother remain close throughout *The Heart of A Woman*. Mary Jane Lupton observes in this regard thus:

On one level, she improves in her ability to care for him and solicit his opinions; on another, she continues the persistent problem of separation begun in *Gather Together* and *Singin' and Swingin'* when she loses touch with his life and needs. (130)

Maya Angelou's conflict with motherhood heightens in *The Heart of A Woman*. When Guy gets in trouble with some gangsters, Maya Angelou feels in a moment of fear that she has been, "capricious and too-often absent mother" (106). The motif of the responsible mother occurs frequently in the series. In *Gather Together in My Name*, Maya Angelou travels alone on a long bus ride to confront Big Mary Dalton who had kidnapped Guy. In an early incident in *The Heart of A Woman* Maya Angelou looks three white school teachers in the eye when they accuse Guy of upsetting some little girls. The Brooklyn gang event is also the result of a girl accusing Guy. Knowing the passions of teenagers, Maya Angelou takes extreme measures to protect her son.

When she confronts Jerry, the gang leader, she threatens to shoot his entire family if anything happens to Guy. Maya Angelou has a gun in a first to prove it.

The confrontation with Jerry reveals Maya Angelou as a strong, aggressive and too impulsive black mother who puts aside her guilt and self doubt in order to defend her son. Maya Angelou says in an interview thus:

I've always been adventurous or up to life. Even not adventurous, but when life says 'Here you are, deal with it; I have dealt with it, or tried to. (Icon, 1997)

Maya Angelou in *The Heart of A Woman* becomes a representative of maternal power. In her dealings with the street gang, Maya Angelou's embodies a type of black woman who can be described as the "outraged mother". These types of outraged mothers are frequently found in the black American Women's slave narratives. Maya Angelou represents the strength and dedication of the black mother.

Maya Angelou's violent reaction in this episode goes back to *I Know Why the Caged Bird Sings*, back to her rape, and back to the vengeful actions that grandmother Baxter and her family took against Mr. Freeman for rapping Maya Angelou. Maya Angelou's violent behavior in handling Jerry may involve an incensing effort to rewrite her own history. Maya Angelou will be aggressive like the Baxter's and she will not be passive like her paternal grandmother Momma Henderson who hit Uncle Willie in the Potato box when the Ku Klux Klan arrived. She also remained submissive when the three offensive white girls taunted her in front of the store. She slapped Maya Angelou and sent her away in *Gather Together in My Name* because Maya challenged a white sales woman. Maya Angelou will do whatever it takes to protect her son. At the same time, her aggression is played out against her fear that she cannot save Guy from harm, an attitude that reveals the vulnerability she feels as mother trying protect her child from any form of danger.

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